

A Survey on Texture Image Descriptors in Computer Vision Applications

Sana Karimian^{1,*}

¹ Faculty of Computer Engineering, Online Computer Vision Research Group

*Corresponding author: sanakarimian.a.f@gmail.com

Abstract

In computer vision, the texture is defined as a function of spatial variation of the intensity of the pixels in the whole image. Texture is one of the main terms used to define objects or concepts of a given image. It is used along with color and shape to describe image contents. Texture analysis plays an important role in computer vision and image processing cases such as medical diagnosis, object recognition, defect detection, visual pattern recognition, noise reduction, etc. Until now different approaches have been proposed to analysis texture images. Texture analysis methods usually are classified into four categories: statistical methods, structural, model-based and transform- based methods. In this paper, the various applications of texture analysis methods are discussed in details. The common step of many computer vision applications is feature extraction. Texture features are so discriminative in many cases. A comparisons study of different texture descriptors is proposed in terms of using variety.

Keywords: Texture, Texture image analysis, Feature extraction, Computer vision, Benchmark texture image datasets

1. INTRODUCTION

Tactile texture defined as tangible feel of a surface and visual texture refers to see the shape or contents of the image [1]. Diagnosis of texture in a human vision system is easily feasible but in the computer vision domain is a complex problem. In the image processing, the texture can be defined as a function of spatial variation of the brightness intensity of the pixels[2]. The texture represents the variations of each level, which measures characteristics such as smoothness, smoothness, coarseness and regularity of each surface in different order directions [2]. Textural images refer to the images in which a specific pattern of intensity distribution is repeated sequentially throughout the image [3]. In the Figure 1, some examples of texture images is shown.

Fig 1: Some example of a textural image

As can be seen in many researches, texture information plays most important role in image analysis. Texture features are more discriminative than color or shape features. In this respect, texture analysis is used in many computer vision applications for feature extraction phase. In this paper a survey is provided on use of texture information in computer vision. Sine now, many different texture descriptors are provided. Most of them is categorized in 4 different categories which is shown in the following table.

Table 1: Categorization of texture descriptors

Categories	Sub-categories
Statistical	Histogram properties Co-occurrence matrixes Local binary patterns Local ternary patterns Laws texture energy
Structural	Primitive pattern units Edge detected features Skeleton representation Morphological operations Scale invariant feature transform
Filter based	Autoregressive (AR) model Fractal models Random field model Texton property model
Model based	Gabor filter Wavelet filter Curvelet Transform features

2. IMAGE RETRIEVAL

Content based image retrieval is one of the most usable computer vision applications which have many attentions by researchers. Image retrieval means retrieving most similar images to the user query image from a huge image database. It is done now based on image contents such as color, texture, object, background, shape, etc. For example in [5], tajeripour et al., proposed a multi step content based image retrieval (CBIR) based on combination modified local binary patterns (MLBP) and morphological operation. In this paper, MLBP is proposed as new lbp-like descriptors as texture analysis operation. Results show that MLBP can provide discriminative features to describe image contents in comparison other texture descriptors such as LBP, LTP, etc. As another example, zhu et al., [22] proposed a content based image retrieval system based on hashing with semantic assistant(SAVH). It's performance study on three well known datasets such as Wiki, MIR Flickr, and NUS-WIDE indicates that SAVH can achieve superior performance over some state-of-the-art techniques.

Dubey et al., used the combination of texture features in multi channels for image retrieval [4]. In this respect, dubey et al., extract texture features using histogram of local binary patterns in different color channels to achieve more discriminative and related features [4].

3. VISUAL SURFACE DEFECT DETECTION

Visual quality inspection is one of the main parts in many industrial applications. Hence, surface defect detection is one of the problems that have received much attention by computer vision researchers. Until now, different methods have been proposed based on texture analysis. In [9], a new noise-resistant and multi-resolution version of LBP is proposed that extracts color and texture features jointly titled NrLBP. Next, a robust algorithm is proposed for detecting abnormalities in surfaces based on proposed NrCLBP [9]. In many industrial products, abnormality disturbs the texture of normal product surface. In this respect, texture features can be used widely to describe defected parts.

Texture information widely used in many other industrial products. For example in [10], one dimensional local binary patterns (1DLBP) is proposed for the first time as an efficient texture descriptors with lower computational complexity in comparison with some other descriptors. Next, a two step algorithm is proposed for stone porosity detection, where, 1DLBP is used in train step to define non-defected parts [10].

4. MEDICAL DIAGNOSIS

Tsarouchi et al., used texture features for breast cancer diagnosis[11]. This study [11] investigates the diagnostic performance of first and second order texture analysis descriptors on apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) lesion maps. Also, a two-step segmentation approach was applied on high b-value diffusion image, based on Fuzzy C-Means (FCM) clustering and edge-based contouring, for defining the lesion region contour.

For example, in [12], texture information in combination of statistical features and time series features provide good results in pap smear classification. Low complexity low rotation sensitivity and high accuracy are major advantages of the [12]. The author proves that local texture information is more efficient than global texture information to describe nucleus part in pap smear image.

5. GENDER CLASSIFICATION

Gender classification is one of the most attention applications in computer vision. Gender classification mostly is used as preprocessing step of face recognition systems. In [14], fekri-ershad proposed a gender classification approach in human face images for smart phones applications. It is done accurately based on local texture information and evaluated kullback-leibler divergence [14]. An evaluated version of k-nearest neighbors is proposed in [14] which uses log likelihood ratio as distance measure. The proposed approach [14] provides classification accuracy about 94.76 on ICPR dataset.

6. IMAGE DENOISING

Fekri-ershad et al., [16] proposed a novel approach for noise reduction as combination of texture processing and text mining techniques. They used real word spelling correction algorithm as input data for texture analysis. Results show higher PSNR ration than many other state-of-the-art noise reduction approaches, especially for textural images.

7. RESULTS

In this section the efficiency of survived papers are evaluated in different applications as shown in the table 2. As can be seen in table 2, in all cases texture descriptors provide good results for computer vision applications.

Table 2. A survey on texture descriptors in computer vision applications in terms of performance evaluation

Computer vision applications	Texture descriptor	Dataset	Accuracy
Surface defect detection [23]	Improved spatial local patterns	Self collected	
Surface defect detection [9]	Modified local binary patterns	Self collected	98.1%
Stone porosity detection [10]	One dimensional local binary pattern	Self collected	97.33%
Texture classification [24]	Gabor filter	Brodatz	94.32%
Texture classification [20]	Improved local quinary patterns	Outex TC-0012	98.81%
Texture classification [18]	NrCLBP	Outex TC-0013	99.83%
Image retrieval [6]	Predefined patterns	Simplicity	82.95%
Image retrieval [5]	Modified local binary patterns	Corel 1k	53.04%
Image retrieval [21]	GLCM + Gabor	Simplicity	86.04%
Image retrieval [22]	Semantic hashing	Wiki	----
Gender classification [14]	Modified local ternary patterns	ICPR	94.76%
Cervical cancer diagnosis [12]	Textural statistical features	Herlev	

8. CONCLUSION

The main aim of this paper was to survive the role of texture features in different computer vision and image processing applications. As it was discussed texture features provide discriminative features which can be used in many different applications. In near all of the cases, texture analysis is used for feature extraction phase of different systems. Low sensitivity to noise, low complexity, high related features and rotation invariant are some of the advantages of texture features.

REFERENCES

- [1] Armi, L., and Fekri-Ershad, Sh. (2019), Texture image analysis and texture image classification methods- a review. *International Online Journal of Image Processing and Pattern Recognition*, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 1-29.
- [2] Tuceryan, M., and Jain, A.K. (1993), Texture analysis, in Handbook of pattern recognition and computer vision. *World Scientific Publisher*, pp. 235-276.
- [3] Fekri-Ershad, Sh., (2018), A review on image texture analysis methods. *International Online Journal of Image Processing and Pattern Recognition*, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 1-63.
- [4] Dubey, S. R., Singh, S. K., and Singh, R. K. (2016), Multichannel decoded local binary patterns for content based image retrieval. *IEEE Transaction on Image Processing*, Vol. 25, No. 9, pp. 4018-4032.

- [5] Tajeripour, F., Saberi, M., and Fekri-Ershad, Sh. (2015), Developing a novel approach for content based image retrieval using modified local binary patterns and morphological transform. *International Arab Journal of Information Technology*, Vol. 12, No. 6, pp. 574-581.
- [6] Hor, N., and Fekri-Ershad, Sh. (2019), Image retrieval approach based on local texture information derived from predefined patterns and spatial domain information. *International Journal of Computer Science Engineering*, Vol. 8, No. 6, pp. 246-254.
- [7] Nguyen, H., Bai, L. (2010), Cosine similarity metric learning for face verification. *In Proc. of 10th Asian Conference on Computer Vision*, pp. 709-720.
- [8] Khamar, K. (2013), Short text classification using KNN based on distance function. *International Journal of advanced research in computer and communication engineering*, Vol. 2, No. 4, pp. 1916-1919
- [9] Fekri-Ershad, Sh., and Tajeripour, F. (2017), Multi-resolution and noise-resistant surface defect detection approach using new version of local binary patterns. *Applied Artificial Intelligence*, Vol. 31, No. 5-6, pp. 395-410.
- [10] Tajeripour, F., and Fekri-Ershad, Sh. (2014), Developing a novel approach for stone porosity computing using modified local binary patterns and single scale retinex. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, Vol. 39, No. 2, pp. 875-889.
- [11] Tsarouchi, M., Vlachopoulos, G. F., Karahaliou, A. N., Costaridou, L. (2019), Diffusion weighted magnetic resonance imaging texture biomarkers for breast cancer diagnosis. *In Proc. of Mediterranean Conference on Medical and Biological Engineering and Computing*. Coimbra, Portugal, pp. 301-305.
- [12] Fekri-Ershad, Sh. (2019), Pap smear classification using combination of global significant value, texture statistical features and time series features. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, Vol. 78, No. 22, pp. 31121-31136.
- [13] Bianconi, F., Bello-Cerezo, R., Napoletano, P. (2017), Improved opponent color local binary patterns: an effective local image descriptor for color texture classification, *Journal of Electronic Imaging*, Vol. 27, No. 1, pp. 011002
- [14] Fekri-Ershad, Sh. (2019), Gender classification in human face images for smart phone applications based on local texture information and evaluated kullback-leibler divergence. *Traitement du Signal*, Vol. 36, No. 6, pp. 507-514.
- [15] Xu, Q., Yang, J., and Ding, S. (2005), Color texture analysis using the wavelet based hidden markov model. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, Vol. 26, pp. 1710-1719
- [16] Fekri-Ershad, Sh., Fakhrahmad, M., and Tajeripour, F. (2018), Impulse noise reduction for texture images using real word spelling correction algorithm and local binary patterns. *International Arab Journal of Information Technology*, Vol. 15, No. 6, pp. 1024-1030.
- [17] Tajeripour F., Rezaei, M., Saberi, M., Fekri-Ershad, Sh. (2011), Texture classification approach based on combination of random threshold vector technique and co-occurrence matrixes. *In Proc. of International Conference on Computer Science and Network Technology*, Harbin, China, pp. 2303-2306.
- [18] Fekri-Ershad, Sh., and Tajeripour, F. (2017), Color texture classification based on proposed impulse-noise resistant color local binary patterns and significant points selection algorithm. *Sensor Review*, Vol. 37, No. 1, pp. 33-42.
- [19] Bianconi, F., and González, E. (2019), Counting local n-ary patterns, *Pattern Recognition Letters*, Vol. 117, pp. 24-29
- [20] Armi, L., and Fekri-Ershad, Sh. (2019), Texture image classification based on improved local quinary patterns. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, Vol. 78, No. 14, pp. 18995-19018.
- [21] Bani, N. T. and Fekri-Ershad, Sh. (2019), Content-based image retrieval based on combination of texture and colour information extracted in spatial and frequency domains. *Electronic Library*, Vol. 37, No. 4, pp. 650-666.
- [22] Zhu, L., Shen, J., Xie, L., Cheng, Z. (2017), Unsupervised visual hashing with semantic assistant for content-based image retrieval. *IEEE Transaction on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, Vol. 29, No. 2, pp. 472-486.
- [23] Fekri-Ershad, Sh., and Tajeripour, F. (2012), A robust approach for surface defect detection based on one dimensional local binary patterns. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, Vol. 5, No. 8, pp. 3197-3203.
- [24] Bianconi, F., and Fernandez, A. (2007), Evaluation of the effects of gabor filter parameters on texture classification. *Pattern Recognition*, Vol. 40, No. 12, pp. 3325-33335.